

Biosorptive removal of methylene blue from aqueous solution by chemically activated watermelon rind as adsorbent

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Abstract : Watermelon rind a low cost agro waste was chemically activated using *ortho* phosphoric acid as the activating agent. The activated watermelon rind (AWR) was evaluated as biosorbent for the removal of basic cationic dye methylene blue from aqueous solution. Batch mode adsorption studies were performed by varying the parameters such as pH, adsorbent dose, contact time, initial dye concentration and temperature. Kinetic studies revealed that the biosorption of dye was rapid onto AWR and follows pseudo-second order kinetic model. The equilibrium data was fit to Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin isotherms and found to fit better to Langmuir isotherm. The maximum loading capacity of AWR for methylene blue was found to be 417.6 mg g⁻¹. Thermodynamic studies confirm that the nature of biosorption of methylene blue by AWR is spontaneous and exothermic in nature. These results suggest that watermelon rind can be an active precursor for the removal of methylene blue from aqueous solution.

Keywords : Watermelon rind, activation, biosorption, methylene blue.

Introduction

Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) rind, a common agricultural by-product, is a natural and rich source of the amino acids and dietary supplements. The rind is reported to have abundant carboxyl and amino groups, which has remarkable capability of binding cations from aqueous solutions¹. Watermelon rind (WR) consists of pectin, citrulline, cellulose, proteins and carotenoids^{2,3}. Only half of the fruit is considered to be edible leaving the other half like rind as waste products. In order to utilize the agro-waste, watermelon rind is investigated as novel adsorbent to eliminate methylene blue a cationic dye from aqueous solution.

The stability and removal efficiency of raw biomass can be further improved by chemical modification and activation⁴. In view of this several agricultural wastes have been chemically modified and proven to be better sorbents for the removal of heavy metals. Hence for the first time, in this study, watermelon rind has been chemically activated using *ortho* phosphoric acid as activating agent and used as a potential biosorbent for sequestration of methylene blue from aqueous solution. Effect of pH, contact time, adsorbent dose, initial dye concentration

and temperature on adsorption was studied. In order to understand the nature of adsorption thermodynamics, equilibrium isotherms and kinetics have been evaluated for experimental data.

Experimental

Preparation of biosorbent :

Watermelon rind (WR) powder was prepared according to the procedure reported in literature⁵. To the WR powder, 1 : 1 *ortho* phosphoric acid was added and stirred well to obtain homogenous mixture. The mixture was then placed in the hot air oven and activated at 110 °C for 4 h. The obtained char was washed several times with double distilled water until the washed solution reaches pH 7. The washed char was dried in oven at 110 °C for 8 h, powdered, sieved and stored in polyethylene bottles for further studies. The final powder was named as activated watermelon rind (AWR)

Biosorption studies :

Batch mode adsorption studies were employed for the removal of methylene blue (MB) from aqueous solution. Parameters such as pH, contact time, adsorbent dose, initial dye concentration and temperature was studied.

Effect of pH was studied by varying the pH from 2–10 and effect of biosorbent dose was studied between 0.5–5 g L⁻¹. The effect of contact time was studied between 10–120 min and sorption capacity of AWR was determined by contacting 1.5 g L⁻¹ of dose with 20 ml of known concentration of dye solutions (50–300 mg L⁻¹). After each study, the solid phase was separated by centrifugation at 5000 rpm and the residual concentration of MB was measured at 665 nm using UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Hitachi U-2800 model). The amount of metal adsorbed to PWR was determined by eq. (1),

$$q_e = (C_0 - C_1) \frac{V}{M} \quad (1)$$

where q_e is the metal uptake (mg/g) by PWR, C_0 and C_1 are initial and final metal concentrations (mg/L), V is the solution volume (L) and M is the mass of the adsorbent (g).

Results and discussion

Activated watermelon rind was investigated for the removal of MB from aqueous solution. The removal was found to be rapid and equilibrium reached in 30 min at optimized dose 0.5 g L⁻¹. The effect of others such as pH, initial dye concentration and temperature are studied and discussed.

Effect of pH on biosorption :

It is well known and extensively reported that pH is an important variable governing the adsorption of metal ions by adsorbent⁶. The solution pH influences metal ion sorption on to active sites of adsorbent due to competition between the metal and H⁺ ions. Thus, the batch equilibrium studies were conducted at different initial pH values in the range of 2–10. It was observed that pH has no effect on removal of methylene blue by AWR. This can be attributed as the electrostatic attraction is not the mechanism operating for the removal of methylene blue by AWR. Hence further experiments were conducted at native pH 7 of the solution.

Kinetics of biosorption :

The rate of dye sorption is important parameter for selecting a waste water treatment system. In order to optimize the contact time for the maximum uptake of MB, contact time was varied between 10 to 120 min. The sorption of MB onto AWR was rapid in first 10 min and equilibrium reached within 30 min. To analyze the mechanism of adsorption of MB ions onto AWR, the experimental data were fit to kinetic models such as pseudo-first order, pseudo-second order and Weber and Morris intraparticle diffusion model. The results are summarized in Table 1.

It can be observed from Table 1 that the correlation coefficients for pseudo-first order model are very low and failed to provide realistic estimate of q_e of adsorbed MB onto AWR. The correlation coefficients for pseudo-second order model was found to be close to one and the experimental q_e values were also close to theoretical values suggesting the appropriateness to the model. In general, the experimental data that fits to pseudo-second order model indicate that the rate limiting step for the process involves chemical reaction.

Kinetic data was further analyzed using intraparticle diffusion model in order to study the steps of diffusion mechanisms. The intraparticle diffusion equation can be written as

$$q_t = k_{int} t^{1/2} + C \quad (2)$$

where k_{int} is the intraparticle diffusion rate constant and C is the intercept related to the thickness of the boundary layer. According to eq. (2) a plot of q_t versus $t^{1/2}$ should give a straight line if the adsorption mechanism follows intraparticle diffusion process only. If the plots show multi linear plots, such plots indicate that two or more steps take place. It was clear from the figure that there are two separate zones present. The first linear plot is due to the immediate utilization of ample active sites on the adsorbent surface and the second linear plot attributed to very slow diffusion of the adsorbate from the surface site into

Table 1. Kinetic parameters for removal of MB onto AWR from aqueous solution (pH 7, dose 0.5 g L⁻¹, initial dye concentration 50 mg L⁻¹ and temperature 303 K)

Dye	Experimental q_e (mg g ⁻¹)	Pseudo-first order constants			Pseudo-second order constants		
		q_e (mg g ⁻¹)	K_1 (min ⁻¹)	R^2	q_e (mg g ⁻¹)	K_2 (g mg ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	R^2
MB	89.3	10.7	0.037	0.8421	90.4	0.032	0.999

the inner pores. Thus initial adsorption of MB by AWR may be governed by intraparticle transport of surface diffusion and later part controlled by pore diffusion. However the intercept of the line fails to pass through the origin which may attribute to the difference in the rate of mass transfer in the initial and final stages of adsorption⁷.

Biosorption isotherms :

In order to evaluate the maximum dye loading capacity of AWR, the adsorbent was contacted with different initial dye concentration (50–300 mg L⁻¹) of MB ions at equilibrium. It was observed that the dye loading capacity of AWR increased with the increase in initial dye concentration and reached a maximum capacity of 417.6 mg g⁻¹. To examine the relationship between dye concentration at equilibrium (C_e) and the dye loading capacity (q_e), equilibrium sorption data of MB were fit to Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin isotherms models and respective constants and correlation coefficients are represented in Table 2.

Table 2. Isotherm constants derived for removal of MB from aqueous solution by AWR (pH 7, dose 0.5 g L⁻¹, time 30 min and temperature 303 K)

Isotherms	Parameters	MB
Freundlich	K_f	1.486
	$1/n$	0.056
	R^2	0.9631
Langmuir	q_{max} (mg g ⁻¹)	416.4
	b (L mg ⁻¹)	0.09
	R^2	0.996
Temkin	A	-152.7
	B	12.29
	R^2	0.997

It is found that the adsorption of MB onto AWR fits better with Langmuir isotherm than the Freundlich and Temkin isotherms. The better fit to Langmuir isotherm is further supported by its respective correlation coefficients, which is a measure of how well predicted values from a forecast model match with the experimental data. The theoretical complete monolayer coverage (V_m) of MB onto AWR was calculated to 416.4 mg g⁻¹ respectively against 417.6 mg g⁻¹ found experimentally.

Thermodynamics of biosorption :

The adsorption of MB on to AWR was studied at

three different temperatures in the range of 30–50 °C. The experimental results showed that adsorption capacity decreased with increase in solution temperature. The decrease in the rate of adsorption with the increase in temperature may be attributed to weakening of adsorptive forces between active sites of adsorbent and adsorbate species. From these results, thermodynamic parameters including the change in free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) were used to describe the thermodynamic behaviour of biosorption of MB ions on to AWR.

The values of change in free energy (ΔG°) were found to be -6.449, -7.286 and -7.814 kJ mol⁻¹ for 303, 313 and 323 K respectively. The negative values indicate that the biosorption of MB ions onto AWR is thermodynamically feasible and is spontaneous process. The decrease in ΔG° values with increase in temperature shows increased feasibility of biosorption at higher temperature. The negative value of ΔH° confirms the exothermic process and the negative ΔS° value suggest a decrease in the randomness of the solid/solution interface during the biosorption.

Desorption studies :

In order to access the reusable potential of AWR, desorption and regeneration studies were performed. 0.1 g of MB loaded AWR was treated with 20 ml of different desorbing agents such as 0.1 M HCl, 0.1 M acetic acid, distilled water and 0.1 M NaOH for 30 min and residual concentration of MB was determined from UV-Vis spectrophotometer. It was found that acetic acid produced highest desorbing percentage compared to other agents. However, the percentage desorption was found to be only 73% for acetic acid. These results suggest that AWR can be used only for one cycle for removal of MB from aqueous solution.

Conclusion

Watermelon rind an agro waste was activated using phosphoric acid and evaluated as low cost biosorbent for the removal of methylene blue from aqueous solution. The removal was found to be rapid and follows pseudo-second order kinetic model. The Langmuir isotherm represents well to the equilibrium data suggesting the monolayer adsorption of MB onto AWR. Thermodynamic stud-

ies reveal that biosorption of MB onto AWR is spontaneous and exothermic in nature. These results conclude that the watermelon rind a non hazardous agro material can be effectively employed in removal of MB from aqueous solution.

References

1. M. R. Agnes and M. P. V. Penelope, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 2005, **1078**, 196.
2. M. Andrew, Z. Yun, Q. Feng, N. Manfred and B. E. Gianna, *J. Carbohydr. Res.*, 2008, **343**, 1212.
3. Y. Q. Siew, K. C. Ngan and S. Peter, *J. Chem. Eng. Process*, 2007, **46**, 386.
4. W. S. W. Ngah and M. A. K. M. Hanafiah, *Bioresour. Technol.*, 2008, **99**, 3935.
5. R. Lakshmipathy and N. C. Sarada, *Desalination and Water Treatment.*, 2013, Doi : 10.1080/19443994.2013.812526.
6. M. Martinez, N. Miralles, S. Hidalgo, N. Fiol, I. Villaescusa and J. Poch, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2006, **133**, 203.
7. K. K. Panday, G. Prasad and V. N. Singh, *Environ. Technol. Lett.*, 1986, **50**, 547.